

Azatriterpenes-V. Synthesis of Ring-A Fused Tetrazoles of Pentacyclic Triterpenoids

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Action of sodium azide on the oximes of methyl oleanonate (1) and methyl betulonate (2) in ethylene chloride in presence of chlorosulphonic acid furnished 4-aza-A-homo-olean-28(13)-lactone-(3,4-d)tetrazole (3) and 4-aza-A-homo-28-oxoallobetulin-(3,4-d)tetrazole (4), respectively.

STEROIDAL tetrazoles are known to possess biological activity and some are of clinical significance¹⁻⁴. In some cases, fusion of tetrazole ring to the steroidal nucleus caused striking changes in their physiological activity. Our continued interest to induce biological activity to physiologically inert pentacyclic triterpenes, which are structurally related to steroids, prompted us to synthesise ring-A fused tetrazoles of triterpenes. Tetrazoles are usually prepared by Schmidt reaction treating the corresponding ketone with excess hydrazoic acid-boron trifluoride etherate^{5,6}.

Cervantes *et al.*⁷ synthesised ring-D fused tetrazoles of androstan and estrone by the action of sodium azide in presence of chlorosulphonic acid in ethylene chloride medium on their 17-one oximes.

In our attempt to synthesise ring-A fused tetrazoles by the action of excess hydrazoic acid-boron trifluoride etherate on the corresponding 3-oxo-pentacyclic triterpenes, afforded ring-A fission products, 3-cyano-4-azido-3,4-seco pentacyclic triterpenes and tetrazoles were not obtained even in traces⁸.

In the present investigation oximes of methyl oleanonate (1) and methyl betulonate (2) in ethylene chloride, were treated with sodium azide (5 mol) in presence of chlorosulphonic acid and the products purified by chromatography over basic alumina (S.M.). By virtue of their elemental and spectral analyses, the products from 1 and 2 were found to be 4-aza-A homo-olean-28(13)lactone (3,4-d) tetrazole (3) and 4-aza-A homo-28-oxoallobetulin (3,4-d) tetrazole (4), respectively.

Pentacyclic triterpene carboxylic acids and their methyl esters of olean group are known to lactonise, and lupane group with the expansion of ring-E, under strong acidic conditions⁹. Even in the present instance both methyl oleanonate and methyl betulonate oximes (1 and 2) lactonised, besides the tetrazole formation, under the strong acidic conditions employed (chlorosulphonic acid). The ir spectra of the reaction products showed absorption around 1750, 1590, 1470 and 1390 cm^{-1} for lactone carbonyl, C=N and N=N. The nmr spectra did not show the methyl ester and ethylenic proton signals indicating lactonisation. They had signals centred around δ 3.15 (m, C_2-H_2). The mass spectra of 3 and 4 had the peaks at 494 ($\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$) conforming to their structures.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (CHCl_3) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The nmr spectra were run in CDCl_3 on XL 100A instrument. All the compounds showed consistent elemental analysis.

Action of sodium azide on oximes (1 and 2) in ethylene chloride in presence of chlorosulphonic acid. A typical experiment: To a suspension of sodium azide (1.2 g) in ethylene chloride (20 ml), chlorosulphonic acid (3 ml) was added dropwise during

the course of 1 h at 10-15°. After 15 min a solution of the oxime (1.25 g) in ethylene chloride (20 ml) was slowly added and stirred for 1 h at 10-15° initially and for another 1 h at room temperature (30-35°). The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The dried ethyl acetate extract furnished a dark brown oily residue (800 mg). It was adsorbed over basic alumina (S.M.) and eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°, 1000 ml), petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (8:2, 1000 ml) and finally with ethyl acetate (500 ml). The petroleum ether and ethyl acetate eluates did not furnish any residue. The petroleum ether-ethyl acetate eluate furnished the tetrazole, crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (100 mg), 3 m.p. 255-260°, 4 325°; Mass M^+ 494 ($C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_4$) for 3 and 4. 3, ν_{max} 1750, 1540, 1470 and 1390 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl, C=N and N=N); δ 3.15 (m, C_2-H_2). 4, ν_{max} 1745, 1535, 1460 and 1390 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl and C=N and N=N); δ 3.15 (m, C_2-H_2).

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